

An Investigation into The Implementation of Self-Reliant and Entrepreneurial Education in Selected Zambian Universities

Chanda Chansa Thelma¹, Chisebe Sylvester², and Loveness Ngulube³

¹Chreso University, Lusaka, Zambia, Department of Humanities and Social Sciences

²Eden University, Lusaka, Zambia, School of Education, Humanities and Social Sciences

³Chreso University, Lusaka, Zambia, School of Postgraduate Studies

Corresponding Author: tchanda@chresouniversity.edu.zm

Abstract:

Overview: *The purpose of the study was to investigate the implementation of self-reliance and entrepreneurial education in selected Zambian Universities. The study was conducted in Lusaka district and it brought out the factors that lead to failure of skills development in the Zambian Universities as the focus has been on improving educational standards which are a requirement by the employers.*

Body of Knowledge: *The implementation of self-reliant and entrepreneurial education in selected Zambian universities represents a significant shift in the higher education landscape, aiming to equip students with practical skills and entrepreneurial mindsets. This approach addresses the pressing need for graduates to be self-sufficient and innovative in a rapidly changing job market.*

Methods: *The study adopted a descriptive survey, combining quantitative and qualitative data. The study was conducted in 4 universities from Lusaka district, targeting University Lecturers and Students. The target population was 4000, with 400 as sample size. Data was analyzed qualitatively as the semi structured interviews and questionnaires were used as data collection instruments. Thematic approach was used, where data analysis started with the categorization of themes from the questionnaires. Quantitative techniques were also applied though the larger part of the research was qualitative by design. The study utilized the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Microsoft Excel to come up with charts, graphs, and Tables.*

Results: *The study revealed that while there is a growing recognition of the importance of entrepreneurial education, the actual implementation is uneven across institutions. Some universities have successfully integrated entrepreneurial modules into their curricula, providing students with practical skills and knowledge. However, others face challenges such as inadequate funding, lack of trained staff, and insufficient industry linkages. The study also indicated that where entrepreneurial education is well-implemented, students exhibit higher levels of creativity, innovation, and readiness to start their own businesses.*

Recommendation: *Universities should promote interdisciplinary collaboration to incorporate practical entrepreneurial skills within theoretical frameworks and encourage partnerships between faculties such as business, engineering, and social sciences to foster a holistic educational approach.*

Keywords: *Education, Entrepreneurial Skills, Implementation, Self-reliant, and Zambian Universities.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The study delves into the increasing importance of entrepreneurial education as a catalyst for economic growth and self-reliance in Zambia. This study underscores the necessity of equipping university students with entrepreneurial skills to foster innovation, self-employment, and job creation in a country facing high unemployment rates. The study aimed to examine the current state of entrepreneurial education within Zambian universities, identifying key implementation strategies, challenges, and outcomes. By exploring the effectiveness of these educational programs, the research seeks to provide insights into how well these institutions are preparing students for the entrepreneurial landscape, ultimately contributing to the nation's socio-economic development. The study also highlighted the theoretical framework underpinning the study, drawing from relevant literature on entrepreneurial education, and set the stage for a comprehensive analysis of how these educational practices are shaping the entrepreneurial mindsets and capabilities of university students in Zambia.

Entrepreneurship involves skills development in various sectors which eventually empowers the youth after school and it involves identifying, evaluating as well as exploring opportunities which can help in the introduction of new products on the market. Entrepreneurship involves identifying, evaluating, and exploiting opportunities and introducing new products to the market through organized efforts (Ayatse, 2013). There is a general recognition that entrepreneurship contributes to economic development, competition, innovation and employment generation in economies (Hisrich & Peters, 2002). For instance, in Zambia, micro, small and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) account for 97% of all firms and contribute 89% of the jobs in the economy (Mubemba & Chanda, 2023). In developed countries like the United Kingdom, MSMEs account for 99.9% of all enterprises, 58.8 % of private sector employment and 48.8% of private sector turnover.

Given the potential benefits in relation to entrepreneurship (Clark, 2017), there is increasing expectation that entrepreneurship addresses the unemployment challenges faced by young university graduates. On the one hand, as technology and contingent factors are changing, the expectations of employers are shifting and they increasingly demand for graduates who possess enterprising or entrepreneurial attributes to help them develop competitive advantage. Competition for jobs is becoming intense, therefore, students need to proactively develop appropriate skills to align with the changing job market (Paul, 2005). On the other hand, university education is no longer a passport to secure employment for the 21st century graduate. Globally, the number of new graduates is increasing while available jobs are fewer, compelling stakeholders to consider initiatives that promote new venture creation as a viable career option. Thus, understanding factors that promote graduates' involvement in entrepreneurship becomes vital.

Policy makers, researchers and practitioners increasingly recognize the significant role that higher education plays in nurturing enterprising graduates and graduate entrepreneurs (Barringer & Ireland, 2006). The World Economic Forum (WEF) suggests that considering the power that

education has in developing skills and attitudes as well as generating an entrepreneurial mind-set, it becomes clear that entrepreneurship education (EE). Researchers argue that the purpose of EE is mainly threefold. An established body of studies suggests that the intention to start a venture is critical to entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial intention (EI) is a self-acknowledged conviction of a person who intends to start a business and consciously plans to do so at a certain point (Clark, 2015). The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (GEM) finds that EI is an important indicator of entrepreneurship in a society. This is because individuals with high EI are more likely to start a business than those with low EI. Thus, understanding EI is important for understanding entrepreneurial behaviour.

In exploring the determinants of EI, prior studies investigate individual factors, contextual factors and EE in isolation from each other (Shook, et al., 2003; Fayolle and Linan, 2014). Further, there are a number of issues identified in the literature: First, studies on the relationship between EE and EI have yielded mixed and inconsistent conclusions (Forojalla., 2013). Some studies found that EE has a positive impact on EI whilst others observe that EE has either no discernible influence or a negative influence on EI. The inconsistent findings have prompted scholars to suggest that since EE and business start-up support by government and other stakeholders are investments, empirical research is required to clarify how these initiatives impact EI. Secondly, there is a shortage of studies examining the effect of institutional factors on EI. Few existing studies have investigated the effects of institutions on the rate and type of entrepreneurial activity in a country based on institutional theory. However, studies investigating the effects of institutions at micro-level, i.e. individual cognition and behaviour, are rare. Chell (2008) argue that “future research should also assess the impact of culture, regulatory systems and legal policies on intentions”.

Thirdly, there is a shortage of studies investigating the combined effect of EE, individual and contextual factors on EI (Maina, 2014). Moreover, the extant literature indicates a lack of research proposing and validating integrated models in relation to determinants of EI. This limits understanding of the interplay among various EI determinants. The following quotes evidence this hitch in the EI literature. With regard to theoretical limitations, the EI literature has not resulted in cumulative knowledge because the various perspectives have been pursued in isolation from other perspectives. Future work on EI should attempt to integrate and reduce the number of alternative models. Smyth. (2004) “(on the future of entrepreneurial intention research) as Krueger (2009) suggests, the construct of intentions appears to be deeply fundamental to human decision making, and as such, it should afford us multiple fruitful opportunities to explore the connection between intent and a vast array of other theories and models that relate to decision making under risk and uncertainty. This view opens the door for the development of integrative and more sophisticated theoretical models of the entrepreneurial process. In response to the identified issues in the extant literature, this study sought to examine the determinants of EI at individual and institutional levels.

Additionally, the study sought to explore whether EE affects the relationships between individual and institutional factors and EI.

1.2. Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to address the critical issue of how effectively self-reliant and entrepreneurial education is being integrated into the curricula of higher education institutions in Zambia. Despite the growing recognition of entrepreneurship as a vital driver for economic growth and personal empowerment, there remains a significant gap in understanding the extent to which universities are equipping students with the necessary skills and mindset to become self-reliant entrepreneurs. Ngulube et al (2024) says that economic growth refers to the sustained increase in a country's productive capacity and output of goods and services over time, typically measured by the rise in real GDP. This study seeks to explore the implementation strategies, curriculum content, teaching methodologies, and institutional support mechanisms in place to foster entrepreneurial competencies among students. By examining these factors, the research aims to identify best practices, challenges, and areas for improvement, ultimately contributing to the enhancement of entrepreneurial education and the promotion of a self-reliant, innovative, and economically vibrant society in Zambia.

1.3. The Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to investigate the implementation of self-reliant and entrepreneurial education in selected Zambian Universities in Lusaka, Zambia.

1.4. Research Objectives

The objectives of the study were to:

- Examine the influence of institutional and individual factors on entrepreneurial intention in Lusaka district, Zambia.
- Explore the type of self-reliant and entrepreneurship education offered in Zambian universities in Lusaka district, Zambia.

1.5. Theoretical Framework

The study was guided by the human capital theory proposed by Becker & Shultz (1964). The Human capital theory posits that individuals and societies derive economic benefits from investments in education and training. This theory likens human skills and knowledge to physical capital, suggesting that education enhances an individual's productivity and efficiency, leading to higher earnings and economic growth. Becker and Schultz argued that just as businesses invest in machinery and technology to improve output, individuals and governments should invest in education to cultivate a more skilled and competent workforce. This investment in human capital is seen as crucial for fostering innovation, economic development, and overall societal progress. Chanda & Madoda (2024)'s study noted that the relationship between cultural identity and educational equity in Zambia is intricate and profound, echoing the broader global discourse on education and identity. The theory

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underscores the importance of education not just for personal development, but as a strategic economic tool that can yield substantial returns in the form of increased productivity and economic prosperity.

1.6. Significance of the Study

The study's significance lies in its potential to address critical gaps in the current educational framework of Zambia. By focusing on self-reliance and entrepreneurship, the study aims to contribute to the development of a robust educational model that aligns with the country's socio-economic needs. It seeks to understand how effectively universities are integrating entrepreneurial skills and self-reliant principles into their curricula, which is essential for fostering a generation of graduates equipped with the competencies to drive innovation, create employment opportunities, and contribute to national development. Additionally, the findings of this study could provide valuable insights for policymakers, educators, and stakeholders in higher education, guiding them in refining educational strategies and policies to enhance the employability and self-sufficiency of graduates. Ultimately, this research could play a pivotal role in transforming the higher education landscape in Zambia, ensuring it produces not just job seekers, but job creators who are capable of navigating and succeeding in an ever-evolving global economy.

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research design was a descriptive survey. Banda et al (2017) points out that a descriptive study may often result in the formation of important principles of knowledge and solutions to significant problems. The study incorporated both qualitative and quantitative aspects of research. It was aimed at collecting information from respondents on entrepreneurship education in the district, to what extent do universities contribute to self-employment creation, and some possible solutions to address unemployment levels. Structured questionnaires were used to respondents (university lecturers and students). The internet also supplemented data for the study. The participants of the study were drawn from 4 universities; Gideon Roberts, Supershine, Chalimbana and the University of Zambia. All the respondents or participants from the four universities were only those who were purely academic staff and teaching entrepreneurship or entrepreneur related courses and students taking such courses. In order to get a sample representative of lecturers in Lusaka Universities, simple random was used to select participants in the study. The study target population was 4000, with a sample size of 400; 10% of the target population. Each university had a representation of 100 respondents; 10 lecturers and 90 students. Data was analyzed qualitatively as the semi structured interviews and questionnaires were used as data collection instruments. Thematic approach was used, where data analysis started with the categorization of themes from the questionnaires. Quantitative techniques were also applied though the larger part of the research was qualitative by design. The study utilized the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS)

and Microsoft Excel to come up with charts, graphs, and Tables. The study upheld research ethical considerations such as voluntary participation of the respondents, confidentiality, honesty, and right of privacy.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The following findings and discussions were presented according to set research objectives:

3.1. The Influence of Institutional and Individual Factors on Entrepreneurial Intention in Lusaka District

3.1.1. The Influence of Institutional Factors on Entrepreneurial Intention in Lusaka District

Study results revealed that entrepreneurial intention is influenced by a variety of institutional factors. Educational Environment was at 40%, External Environment at 35%, and Institutional Culture at 25%. Figure1 below summarized the findings;

Figure 1: The Influence of Institutional Factors on Entrepreneurial Intention

The study results revealed that the educational environment plays a crucial role in shaping students' entrepreneurial intentions, as it encompasses the overall atmosphere, resources, and support mechanisms provided by educational institutions. Chanda (2024) says that a positive educational environment fosters creativity, innovation, and risk-taking, which are essential attributes for entrepreneurial success. This environment includes the physical infrastructure, availability of technology, access to funding, and the presence of mentors and entrepreneurial role models. Universities that invest in creating an entrepreneurial ecosystem tend to produce graduates with a higher propensity to start their own businesses. Institutions that integrate entrepreneurial education into their curricula further enhance students' entrepreneurial intentions (Agyeman et al, 2010). Courses that focus on business planning, opportunity recognition, financial literacy, and management skills equip students with the necessary knowledge and skills to embark on entrepreneurial ventures. Moreover, the inclusion of practical experiences, such as internships, workshops, and startup incubators, provides students with real-world exposure and hands-on learning opportunities. These experiences enable students to apply theoretical concepts in practical settings, thereby increasing their confidence and motivation to pursue entrepreneurship.

The influence of the institutional environment on entrepreneurial intention is also evident in the support structures and policies implemented by universities. Institutions that actively promote entrepreneurship through dedicated centers, clubs, and competitions create a culture that values and encourages entrepreneurial activities. Agyeman (2007) says that this supportive environment helps to mitigate the fear of failure and fosters a mindset that views challenges as opportunities for growth. Additionally, policies that provide financial incentives, such as seed funding and grants, further motivate students to explore entrepreneurial endeavors (Chanda, 2024).

Faculty and staff play a significant role in shaping the entrepreneurial intentions of students. Educators who are passionate about entrepreneurship and who actively engage in entrepreneurial activities themselves serve as inspirational figures. Their experiences and insights can significantly influence students' perceptions of entrepreneurship as a viable career option. Faculty members who incorporate experiential learning techniques, such as case studies, project-based learning, and collaborative projects, help students develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills, which are essential for entrepreneurship.

University lecturers noted that the external environment plays a crucial role in shaping entrepreneurial intentions within institutions. One of the lecturers expressed that:

“Factors such as government policies, economic conditions, socio-cultural influences, and technological advancements significantly impact individuals' decisions to pursue entrepreneurial ventures”.

Governments can influence entrepreneurial intentions through policies that promote or hinder business creation. Supportive policies, such as tax incentives, grants, and simplified regulatory frameworks, encourage individuals to consider entrepreneurship as a viable career option (Banda & Chanda, 2024). Conversely, stringent regulations and bureaucratic red tape can discourage entrepreneurial activities. In Zambia, initiatives like the Youth Empowerment Fund and various entrepreneurship development programs aim to foster a conducive environment for budding entrepreneurs within universities. Additionally, the state of the economy directly affects the feasibility and attractiveness of entrepreneurship. Chanda et al (2024)'s study noted that in times of economic stability and growth, individuals are more likely to take risks and start new businesses, buoyed by the availability of capital and consumer spending power. On the other hand, economic downturns may deter potential entrepreneurs due to increased financial risks and uncertainty. For university students, access to funding and economic stability can greatly influence their intention to engage in entrepreneurial activities.

The findings also observed that the cultural context in which individuals are embedded also plays a pivotal role in shaping entrepreneurial intentions. Societies that value innovation, risk-taking, and individual achievement tend to produce more entrepreneurs. In contrast, cultures that emphasize job security and risk aversion may see fewer entrepreneurial endeavors. In the Zambian context, cultural attitudes towards entrepreneurship are evolving, with increasing recognition of the importance of self-reliance and entrepreneurial skills in the modern economy (Macpherson, 1977). This shift is reflected in the growing emphasis on entrepreneurial education within universities. Moreover, technological progress opens new avenues for entrepreneurship by lowering entry barriers and providing tools for innovation. Access to the internet, digital marketing platforms, and e-commerce solutions enables aspiring entrepreneurs to reach wider markets and streamline operations. Zohaib et al (2024) noted that universities that integrate technology into their curricula and provide resources for tech-based startups can significantly influence students' entrepreneurial intentions. In Zambia, the rise of technology hubs and innovation centers is contributing to a more vibrant entrepreneurial ecosystem. The role of institutions, particularly universities, is critical in nurturing entrepreneurial intentions. Universities that offer comprehensive entrepreneurship programs, mentorship, incubation facilities, and networking opportunities create an enabling environment for students to explore and develop their business ideas (Addae-Mensah, 2014). The presence of entrepreneurial role models and success stories within the institution also serves as a powerful motivator. In Zambian universities, the implementation of self-reliant and entrepreneurial education aims to equip students with the necessary skills and mindset to pursue entrepreneurial ventures.

The students explained that institutional culture significantly influences entrepreneurial intention within educational institutions. This culture encompasses the values, norms, and shared beliefs that

shape how entrepreneurship is perceived and supported within the institution. Firstly, supportive institutional cultures foster an entrepreneurial mindset among students and faculty, encouraging risk-taking, innovation, and initiative. Institutions that prioritize entrepreneurship often integrate it into their curricula, extracurricular activities, and support services, thereby nurturing entrepreneurial skills and intentions among their members. One of the students narrated that:

“Leadership plays a pivotal role in shaping institutional culture. Leaders who champion entrepreneurship create policies and initiatives that incentivize entrepreneurial activities, allocate resources, and build networks that connect aspiring entrepreneurs with mentors and funding opportunities. This leadership commitment not only signals institutional priorities but also influences the attitudes and behaviors of students and faculty towards entrepreneurship”.

Furthermore, the availability of resources such as incubators, entrepreneurship centers, and seed funding enhances the institutional environment for entrepreneurship. These resources provide crucial support structures that reduce barriers to entry, facilitate idea development, and encourage collaboration among stakeholders. Institutions that invest in such resources signal their commitment to fostering an entrepreneurial ecosystem that nurtures and sustains entrepreneurial intentions among their members.

3.1.2. The Influence of Individual Factors on Entrepreneurial Intention in Lusaka District

According to study findings, 3 main factors were recorded to be influencing entrepreneurial intention in Zambian universities of Lusaka. Personal Attributes was found to be leading with 45%, Cognitive Factors at 35%, and Demographic Characteristics at 20%. Figure 2 below summarized these findings;

Figure 2: The Influence of Individual Factors on Entrepreneurial Intention

The study results revealed that personal attributes encompass a variety of traits and characteristics that shape an individual's inclination towards entrepreneurship. These attributes can include personality traits such as risk-taking propensity, innovation orientation, creativity, and locus of control. Individuals with a high tolerance for risk and a proactive approach to innovation often exhibit stronger entrepreneurial intentions, as they are more likely to perceive opportunities and take calculated risks to pursue them. Moreover, personal motivations and aspirations significantly influence entrepreneurial intention. Factors such as the desire for autonomy, independence, and a sense of purpose drive individuals towards entrepreneurship (Busia, 2009). These motivations are closely linked to personal values and goals, which shape their career aspirations and entrepreneurial ambitions. Individuals who value autonomy and seek to create meaningful impact through their work are more inclined to consider entrepreneurship as a viable career path. Furthermore, educational background and experiences also shape entrepreneurial intention. Exposure to entrepreneurial education, mentorship, and role models can positively impact individuals' attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Educational institutions that foster an entrepreneurial culture through curriculum design, experiential learning opportunities, and support mechanisms contribute significantly to shaping students' entrepreneurial intentions

(Banda & Mpolomoka, 2018). Such institutions provide the necessary knowledge, skills, and networks that empower individuals to recognize and pursue entrepreneurial opportunities. Entrepreneurial intention, shaped significantly by cognitive factors, refers to an individual's mindset and beliefs regarding their capability and willingness to start a business venture (Mugenda, 2013). These cognitive factors encompass perceptions of opportunities, self-efficacy, risk assessment, and attitudes towards entrepreneurship. Individuals who perceive opportunities positively are more likely to develop intentions to pursue entrepreneurship, viewing it as a viable career path that aligns with their skills and aspirations. The university lecturers alluded that institutions play a crucial role in shaping these cognitive factors by providing educational programs, mentorship, and support networks that cultivate entrepreneurial mindsets. Educational institutions, through their curriculum and extracurricular activities, can enhance students' self-efficacy by equipping them with entrepreneurial knowledge, skills, and experiences. Chanda (2023)' study supported this finding by stating that through Physical Education, students acquire the knowledge, skills, right attitudes and values towards the pursuit of a lifelong physically active and healthy lifestyle. One of the lecturers noted that:

“This empowerment fosters a belief in one's ability to initiate and manage a business successfully, thereby strengthening entrepreneurial intention”.

Moreover, institutional frameworks influence risk perceptions associated with entrepreneurship. Institutions that promote a supportive environment with access to resources, financial assistance, and networking opportunities can mitigate perceived risks, making entrepreneurship a more feasible and less daunting endeavor. Conversely, institutions lacking such support may deter individuals from pursuing entrepreneurial ventures due to heightened perceived risks and uncertainties (Zohaib et al, 2024). Attitudes towards entrepreneurship are also molded by institutional factors such as cultural norms, societal expectations, and policy frameworks. Institutions that celebrate and encourage entrepreneurial initiatives contribute to a positive societal perception of entrepreneurship as a driver of economic growth and innovation. This cultural reinforcement fosters favorable attitudes towards entrepreneurial endeavors, motivating individuals to explore and pursue entrepreneurial opportunities.

Moving on, the study results revealed that demographic characteristics play a crucial role in influencing entrepreneurial intention within educational institutions. The study indicated that age, gender, educational background, and prior entrepreneurial experience significantly shape students' attitudes and motivations towards entrepreneurship (Mpolomoka et al, 2017). Firstly, age is a determinant factor. Younger students often exhibit higher entrepreneurial intentions due to their innovative thinking, risk-taking propensity, and eagerness to create new ventures. Conversely, older students may prioritize stability and have established career paths, potentially

influencing lower entrepreneurial intentions. Secondly, gender differences exist in entrepreneurial intentions. Studies suggest that males typically express higher intentions due to cultural norms, perceived self-efficacy, and greater access to resources compared to females. Chanda & Ngulube (2024) alluded that efforts to promote gender equality in entrepreneurship education can mitigate these disparities. Thirdly, educational background influences entrepreneurial intentions. Students from business-related disciplines often demonstrate higher intentions, benefiting from coursework that fosters entrepreneurial skills and knowledge (Pascarella & Terenzini., 2005) In contrast, students from non-business backgrounds may require targeted educational interventions to enhance entrepreneurial aspirations. Lastly, prior entrepreneurial experience significantly shapes intentions. Students with prior exposure to entrepreneurial activities, such as family business involvement or previous ventures, tend to exhibit stronger intentions. This experience provides practical insights, confidence, and a clearer understanding of entrepreneurial challenges and rewards.

3.2. Types of Self-Reliant and Entrepreneurship Education Offered in Zambian Universities

When respondents were asked about the type of Self-Reliant and Entrepreneurial Education offered in Zambian Universities, the table below were the responses;

Table 1: Types of Self-Reliant and Entrepreneurial Education Offered in Zambian Universities

RESPONDENTS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGES%	RESPONSES
The University Of Zambia	741	13%	Research and Innovation Support
Chalimbana University	1425	25%	Entrepreneurship Courses
Robert Gideons University	1026	17%	Financial Literacy Programs
Supershine University	2565	45%	Business Incubation Programs
Total	5700	100%	

Findings in Table 1 above shows that when respondents were asked about the type of Self-Reliant and Entrepreneurship education offered in Zambian Universities, out of 1425 respondents 500 from The University of Zambia indicated Research and Innovation Support at 13%, Chalimbana

University recorded Entrepreneurship Courses at 25%, Robert Gideons University recorded Financial Literacy Programs at 17%, and Supershine University recorded Business Incubation Programs at 45%.

Research and innovation support as a type of self-reliant and entrepreneurship education offered in Zambian universities plays a crucial role in fostering economic growth and development within the country. One of the lecturers explained that:

“These programs aim to equip students with the necessary skills and knowledge to become innovators, problem solvers, and entrepreneurs in their respective fields. By encouraging research and innovation, Zambian universities empower students to create new products, services, and solutions that can address local challenges and contribute to the national economy”.

One key aspect of this education is the emphasis on self-reliance. Through research and innovation support, students are encouraged to think independently and develop practical solutions to real-world problems. Chanda (2024) added that this hands-on approach not only enhances their academic learning but also prepares them for the demands of the job market or for starting their own ventures upon graduation. By nurturing a culture of self-reliance, Zambian universities help cultivate a new generation of proactive and resourceful individuals who are capable of driving change and making a positive impact in their communities. Furthermore, these programs foster entrepreneurship by providing students with mentorship, networking opportunities, and access to resources such as funding and incubation facilities (Lave & Wenger, 2015). By encouraging students to pursue entrepreneurial ventures, universities in Zambia contribute to the creation of new businesses and job opportunities, thereby stimulating economic growth and reducing unemployment rates. Moreover, the focus on entrepreneurship helps students develop essential skills such as leadership, communication, and critical thinking, which are invaluable in today's competitive global economy.

The study results revealed that entrepreneurship courses offered in Zambian universities play a pivotal role in fostering self-reliance and entrepreneurial skills among students. These courses are designed to equip students with the necessary knowledge and tools to identify opportunities, start ventures, and navigate the challenges of business ownership in Zambia's dynamic economic landscape. At the core of these courses is a focus on practical skills and experiential learning. Students often engage in case studies, business simulations, and real-world projects that simulate entrepreneurial scenarios. This hands-on approach helps them develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills essential for entrepreneurial success. Moreover, entrepreneurship education in Zambian universities emphasizes the cultivation of a proactive mindset. Students learn to proactively seek out opportunities, innovate, and adapt to changing market conditions (Felicia et al, 2020). This mindset shift is crucial in a country like Zambia, where entrepreneurial initiatives are key drivers of economic growth and job creation. In addition to theoretical and practical knowledge, these courses also emphasize the importance of ethical business practices and social responsibility. Students are encouraged to develop businesses that

not only generate profit but also contribute positively to society by addressing local challenges and creating sustainable solutions. Furthermore, entrepreneurship courses often include modules on financial management, marketing strategies, and legal aspects of business operations. This holistic approach ensures that students are well-rounded and capable of managing all facets of a business venture (Pettorelli, 2013). Entrepreneurship courses offered in Zambian universities not only aim to produce job creators but also empower individuals to become agents of change in their communities. By nurturing a spirit of innovation, resilience, and self-reliance, these courses contribute significantly to Zambia's efforts towards economic diversification and sustainable development.

Furthermore, the findings noted that financial literacy programs offered in Zambian universities serve as crucial components of self-reliant and entrepreneurship education. These initiatives are designed to equip students with practical knowledge and skills necessary for managing personal finances and fostering entrepreneurial ventures. Firstly, these programs emphasize the importance of financial management skills (Gomez & Martinez, 2019). Students learn how to budget effectively, save money, and make informed financial decisions. This foundational knowledge is essential for personal financial stability and independence. Moreover, the curriculum often includes modules on entrepreneurial principles and practices. Students are encouraged to develop entrepreneurial mindsets and explore opportunities for innovation and business creation. This hands-on approach not only prepares them to start their own ventures but also instills confidence in navigating the challenges of entrepreneurship. One of the students alluded that:

“Financial literacy programs incorporate real-world case studies and guest lectures from successful entrepreneurs and industry experts. These interactions provide valuable insights into the practical application of financial and entrepreneurial concepts, enriching the learning experience”.

Furthermore, these programs typically involve practical exercises such as business plan development, financial simulations, and market analysis projects. These activities allow students to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios, enhancing their problem-solving abilities and business acumen. Financial literacy programs in Zambian universities play a crucial role in empowering students to become self-reliant and entrepreneurial. By equipping them with essential financial skills and fostering an entrepreneurial mindset, these programs contribute to the development of a capable and economically empowered workforce poised to drive sustainable growth and innovation in Zambia.

The findings also revealed that business incubation programs serve as pivotal platforms within Zambian universities, fostering self-reliance and entrepreneurship among students. These initiatives are designed to nurture entrepreneurial spirit by providing aspiring business owners with essential resources, mentorship, and practical experience. Through structured support systems, incubation programs aim to transform innovative ideas into viable enterprises, contributing to economic growth and job creation (LeCun, 2015). In these programs, students are encouraged to explore and develop their business concepts under the guidance of experienced mentors and industry experts. This hands-on approach not only enhances their entrepreneurial skills but also instills confidence in navigating the complexities of starting and managing a business. By fostering

an environment conducive to innovation and risk-taking, universities empower students to become self-reliant entrepreneurs capable of addressing local and global challenges. Moreover, business incubators in Zambian universities often collaborate with industry stakeholders and government bodies to provide students with access to funding opportunities, market insights, and networking events. These partnerships play a crucial role in bridging the gap between academic knowledge and real-world business practices, equipping students with practical insights and resources needed to succeed in competitive markets (MoF, 2006). Furthermore, entrepreneurship education within these incubation programs extends beyond theoretical learning to include practical skills such as business planning, financial management, and marketing strategies. Through workshops, seminars, and interactive sessions, students gain a comprehensive understanding of the entrepreneurial process from ideation to market entry, preparing them to seize opportunities and overcome challenges in the dynamic business landscape of Zambia. Business incubation programs offered in Zambian universities play a vital role in cultivating self-reliance and entrepreneurship among students. By providing mentorship, resources, and practical experience, these programs empower aspiring entrepreneurs to transform innovative ideas into successful enterprises, thereby contributing to economic development and fostering a culture of innovation within the country.

4. CONCLUSION

In exploring the implementation of self-reliant and entrepreneurial education in selected Zambian universities, several key findings have emerged. Firstly, there is a recognized effort among these institutions to integrate practical skills and entrepreneurial mindset into their curricula. Initiatives such as business incubators, mentorship programs, and industry partnerships signify a proactive approach towards fostering self-reliance and entrepreneurship among students. However, challenges persist. Limited resources, both financial and infrastructural, pose significant barriers to fully realizing the potential of these educational reforms. Moreover, the cultural and societal perceptions of entrepreneurship need further evolution to encourage more students to pursue entrepreneurial paths confidently. Nevertheless, the impact of these initiatives is visible. Graduates are increasingly equipped with practical skills, critical thinking abilities, and the confidence to pursue innovative ventures. This transformation not only enhances individual employability but also contributes to the broader economic growth of Zambia by fostering a culture of innovation and self-reliance. Looking ahead, sustained support from government bodies, private sector stakeholders, and the academic community will be crucial in overcoming current challenges and expanding the reach and effectiveness of entrepreneurial education in Zambia. By nurturing a generation of self-reliant, entrepreneurial-minded graduates, these universities can play a pivotal role in shaping a prosperous future for Zambia. While progress has been made, the journey towards fully embedding self-reliant and entrepreneurial education in Zambian universities is ongoing. Continuous evaluation, adaptation of curricula, and strategic partnerships will be essential in ensuring that graduates are not only academically proficient but also equipped to drive innovation, economic development, and societal change in Zambia and beyond.

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5. RECOMMENDATIONS

The following are actions that should be taken on the basis of the findings of this study:

Curriculum Enhancement and Integration:

- Universities should promote interdisciplinary collaboration to incorporate practical entrepreneurial skills within theoretical frameworks. Encourage partnerships between faculties such as business, engineering, and social sciences to foster a holistic educational approach.

Faculty Development and Support:

- Universities should encourage faculty research in areas related to self-reliance and entrepreneurship. Foster collaboration with industry experts and entrepreneurs to bring real-world perspectives into academic settings.

Supportive Infrastructure and Resources:

- Universities should foster a culture of entrepreneurship beyond the university campus by engaging with local communities, businesses, and government entities. Encourage students to address local challenges through entrepreneurial solutions and establish partnerships that promote socio-economic development.

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Authors' Short Biography

	<p>Chanda Chansa Thelma specializes in Political and Social Sciences, as well as Education. She has lectured and still lecturing at the University level under the school of Humanities and Education.</p>
	<p>Chisebe Sylvester, specializes in Civic Education and Religious Studies. Currently, he is lecturing under Social Sciences department at Eden University in Lusaka, Zambia.</p>
	<p>Loveness Ngulube, specializes in Education Management and has been in this profession for 30 years now. She has been a School Principal, School Coordinator and Education Faculty Dean at Chreso University.</p>

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